

**ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY FOR STUDENTS IN
NON-PHILOLOGICAL EDUCATION USING SUGGESTOPEDIA TEACHING
METHOD**

Ibragimova Sevinch Mansurbekovna

Student of Urgut branch of

Samarkand State University named Sharof Rashidov

E-mail address: sevinch.ibragimova5696@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8046127>

***Abstract.** This article is devoted to the issues of methodology in teaching English to non-philological students. This article discusses using the Suggestopedia teaching method as an important source for teaching foreign languages.*

***Key words:** Suggestopedia, suggestopedic instruction, active concert, passive concert, psychological barriers.*

**МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА СТУДЕНТАМ
НЕФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТЕЙ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ МЕТОДА
СУГГЕСТОПЕДИИ**

***Аннотация.** Данная статья посвящена вопросам методологии преподавания английского языка студентам-нефилологам. В этой статье рассматривается использование метода суггестопедии в качестве важного источника для преподавания иностранных языков.*

***Ключевые слова:** суггестопедия, суггестопедическое обучение, активный концерт, пассивный концерт, психологические барьеры.*

INTRODUCTION

Suggestopedia is a method of teaching a foreign language in which students learn quickly by being made to feel relaxed, interested, and positive. The method is developed because of the argument that students naturally face psychological barriers, which refer to a variety of internal distractions (worry, anxiety, fatigue, boredom, fear, etc.). This method was developed in the 1970s by the Bulgarian psychiatrist and educator Georgi Lozanov. Suggestopedia is often regarded as pseudoscience because it hasn't been used on a large scale with the correct methodology and testing. It is a compound word "suggestion" and "pedagogy". Learners are encouraged to consciously use the relaxation techniques and physical postures with low lighting and soft music in the background. Lozanov believes it creates a level of relaxed concentration that facilitates the intake and retention of huge quantities of material. Another aspect that differs from other methods is the use of soft comfortable chairs and dim lighting in the classroom (other factors believed to create a more relaxed state of mind). Using this method, Lozanov's foreign language classes have demonstrated rates of learning three times faster than those achieved in the best intensive programs in the United States. A number of authors have investigated various aspects of suggestopedia as applied to university-level foreign language learning. Bordon and Schuster have applied the principles of suggestion to Spanish instruction over one academic quarter and report that students learned up to three times faster than students taught by the conventional audiolingual method. Kurkov describes a preliminary experiment with a suggestopedic.

MAIN PART

It is a compound word "suggestion" and "pedagogy". Learners are encouraged to consciously use the relaxation techniques and physical postures with low lighting and soft music in the background. Lozanov believes it creates a level of relaxed concentration that facilitates the intake and retention of huge quantities of material. Another aspect that differs from other methods is the use of soft comfortable chairs and dim lighting in the classroom (other factors believed to create a more relaxed state of mind). Using this method, Lozanov's foreign language classes have demonstrated rates of learning three times faster than those achieved in the best intensive programs in the United States. A number of authors have investigated various aspects of suggestopedia as applied to university-level foreign language learning. Bordon and Schuster have applied the principles of suggestion to Spanish instruction over one academic quarter and report that students learned up to three times faster than students taught by the conventional audiolingual method. Kurkov describes a preliminary experiment with a suggestopedic.

The playful design of many exercises in suggestopedic instruction is likely to produce such kind of experience, e.g. a joy of learning and curiosity. self autonomous development of knowledge, especially on a long term basis, is promoted. It is a compound word "suggestion" and "pedagogy". Learners are encouraged to consciously use the relaxation techniques and physical postures with low lighting and soft music in the background. Lozanov believes it creates a level of relaxed concentration that facilitates the intake and retention of huge quantities of material. Another aspect that differs from other methods is the use of soft comfortable chairs and dim lighting in the classroom (other factors believed to create a more relaxed state of mind). Using this method, Lozanov's foreign language classes have demonstrated rates of learning three times faster than those achieved in the best intensive programs in the United States. A number of authors have investigated various aspects of suggestopedia as applied to university-level foreign language learning. Bordon and Schuster have applied the principles of suggestion to Spanish instruction over one academic quarter and report that students learned up to three times faster than students taught by the conventional audiolingual method It is a compound word "suggestion" and "pedagogy". Learners are encouraged to consciously use the relaxation techniques and physical postures with low lighting and soft music in the background. Lozanov believes it creates a level of relaxed concentration that facilitates the intake and retention of huge quantities of material. Another aspect that differs from other methods is the use of soft comfortable chairs and dim lighting in the classroom (other factors believed to create a more relaxed state of mind). Using this method, Lozanov's foreign language classes have demonstrated rates of learning three times faster than those achieved in the best intensive programs in the United States. A number of authors have investigated various aspects of suggestopedia as applied to university-level foreign language learning. Bordon and Schuster have applied the principles of suggestion to Spanish instruction over one academic quarter and report that students learned up to three times faster than students taught by the conventional audiolingual method. Kurkov describes a preliminary experiment with a suggestopedic.

It is a compound word "suggestion" and "pedagogy". Learners are encouraged to consciously use the relaxation techniques and physical postures with low lighting and soft music in the background. Lozanov believes it creates a level of relaxed concentration that facilitates the intake and retention of huge quantities of material. Another aspect that differs from other methods is the use of soft comfortable chairs and dim lighting in the classroom (other factors believed to

create a more relaxed state of mind). Using this method, Lozanov's foreign language classes have demonstrated rates of learning three times faster than those achieved in the best intensive programs in the United States. A number of authors have investigated various aspects of suggestopedia as applied to university-level foreign language learning. Bordon and Schuster have applied the principles of suggestion to Spanish instruction over one academic quarter and report that students learned up to three times faster than students taught by the conventional audiolingual method. Kurkov describes a preliminary experiment with a suggestopedic.

REFERENCES

1. Brown, H.Douglas. 2001. Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy. San Fransisco: Longman
2. Harmer, Jeremy. 2003. The Practice of English Language Teaching. Malaysia: Longma
3. Larsen, Diane, et.al.2001. Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching. Oxford: Oxford University Press
4. Murcia, Marianne Celce. 1991. Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language. Boston: Heinle and Heinle PublishersHornby, AS. 2008. Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary. Oxford: Oxford University Press
5. Richards, Jack C. 1992. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
6. Richards, Jack C. 1990. Longman Dictionary of Applied Linguistics. Hongkong: Longman
7. http://www.englishraven.com/method_suggest., August 28th 2010
8. <http://www.delphin-international.com/ResourceCenter/Suggesto>, August 29th 2010
9. http://www.jwelforddemon.co.uk/brainwaremap/t_suggest , August 28th 2010
10. <http://www.delphininternational.com/ResourceCenter/suggesto>, August 30th 2010